

Studies on Some Less Familiar Ferrocyanogen Complexes. Part XIV. Composition, Properties, and Colloidal Behaviour of Titanium (III & IV) Ferricyanides

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Ti(III & IV) ferrocyanogen complexes have been prepared by mixing the reactants in equimolecular proportions. The dried precipitates have the compositions $KTi^{III}Fe^{III}(CN)_6$, $Ti^{IV}Fe^{III}(CN)_6$, and $Ti^{IV}Fe^{III}(CN)_6$. The freshly precipitated complexes exhibit both hydrolytic and adsorptive properties. $KTi^{III}Fe^{III}(CN)_6$ and $Ti^{IV}Fe^{III}(CN)_6$ hydrolyse more than $Ti^{III}Fe^{III}(CN)_6$ does. Unlike other metal ferro- and ferricyanides, the metal ion is adsorbed more than the ferrocyanogen ions. Titanic ferrocyanide could be obtained as a negatively charged sol by mixing $TiCl_4$ and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ in the ratio of 0.69:1 respectively.

The results of conductometric, thermometric, and potentiometric titrations, carried out both in the direct and reverse order, confirm the results of chemical analysis and also provide evidence for the adsorption complexes.

Amongst the metallic ferro- and ferricyanides, the study of titanium complexes has received very little attention. Recently amperometric studies on the interaction of Ti(III) with potassium ferro- and ferricyanides and that of Ti(IV) with potassium ferrocyanide were carried out in this laboratory¹. The results obtained, although not conclusive, were interesting enough and hence needed a more systematic and critical study. This communication deals with our investigations on the properties, colloidal behaviour, and composition of these complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

To a solution of titanous chloride (150 ml, 12.5% w/v, containing 12.5% HCl) was added ~~specifically~~ pure titanium metal (10 g.) and dry HCl gas was passed into it. $TiCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ crystals² were dissolved in air-free, double distilled water; the strength was determined by adding a known volume to an acidified ferric alum solution and titrating the resulting ferrous sulphate against potassium permanganate. A layer of kerosene was kept over the solution throughout the investigation.

Titanium chloride ($TiCl_3$, 12% w/v soln. containing 15% HCl, BDH) was used for preparing the solution and the strength determined as above, after reducing a known volume in Jones' reductor.

Potassium ferro- and ferricyanide solutions were prepared by dissolving A. R. and recrystallised samples respectively in double distilled water. The solutions were stored in amber-coloured bottles and strengths determined by the usual methods³.

1. Malik, this *Journal*, 1961, **38**, 303.

2. Mallor, "Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. VII, p. 74.

3. Cumming and Kay, "Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 1956, pp. 155, 173.

Analysis of the Complexes.—A 'neutral' sample of titanium(III) ferrocyanide was prepared by adding equal volumes of the reactants of the same concentration ($M/10$). The precipitate was centrifuged, washed first with water and then with 50% ethanol, followed by final washings with absolute ethanol and ether. The originally yellow precipitate changed to a chocolate-brown colour by this treatment. It was dried for a number of days in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 (conc.). The 'neutral' complexes of Ti(III) ferrocyanide and Ti(IV) ferrocyanide were also obtained in a similar manner. The Ti(III) complex was brownish yellow and the Ti(IV) complex was dark brown in colour.

The method of decomposition of the complex and subsequent estimation of titanium and iron as oxides were the same as used in the analysis of ferrocyanide titanium⁴. Potassium was estimated as dipotassium monosodium cobaltinitrite⁵ and the amount of the cyanogen present in the complex was determined by Volhard's method⁶. Experiments were performed in duplicate. The components were found to have the following formulas:

Titanous ferrocyanide: $K_{1.0109} Ti_{1.0001} Fe, (CN)_{5.946}$; $K_{1.0009} Ti, Fe_{1.004} (CN)_{5.878}$.

Titanous ferricyanide: $Ti_{1.006} Fe, (CN)_{6.004}$; $Ti, Fe_{1.018}, (CN)_{6.061}$.

Titanic ferrocyanide: $Ti, Fe_{1.57}, (CN)_{6.493}$; $Ti, Fe_{1.048}, (CN)_{6.383}$.

FIG. 1

- (a) Adsorption of $TiCl_3$ on $K Ti^{III} Fe^{III} (CN)_6$.
 (b) " " $TiCl_4$ " $Ti^{IV} Fe^{III} (CN)_6$.
 (c) " " $TiCl_3$ " $Ti^{III} Fe^{III} (CN)_6$.

Titanic Ferrocyanide Sol.—The freshly precipitated complex showed a tendency to pass into the colloidal state on washing either with water or dilute solution of the complexing agent. Determination of optimum conditions for sol formation and study of the colloidal properties were therefore undertaken. On employing the method of double decomposition, it was found that fairly stable sol could be obtained by using a slight excess of potassium ferrocyanide [$Fe(CN)_6$; $Ti=1:0.89$]. The usual method of obtaining ferrocyanide sol was employed with the only precaution that fairly dilute solution of titanic chloride was used and it was added dropwise to potassium ferrocyanide solution with constant stirring (mixing the reactants in the reverse order invariably resulted in the formation of a precipitate). The undialysed sol, although negatively charged (as found by electrophoresis in Burton's tube), behaved curiously towards electrolytes. Coagulation experiments with

4. Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", Vol. I, 5th ed., 1939, p. 983.

5. Cumming and Kay, *op. cit.*, p. 382.

6. Scott, *op. cit.*, p. 861.

electrolyte, forming what are known as cationic and anionic series, revealed that both cations and anions affected the precipitation to the same extent.

Adsorption.—Adsorption of either of the reactants on the different complexes was studied by employing 1 g. of the freshly precipitated compounds. The results are shown in Fig. 4. The adsorption of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ and $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ on their complexes was negative.

Hydrolytic Behaviour.—For studying the hydrolysis of the various complexes, the solutions of the reactants for a particular complex were mixed in such quantities as to provide 1.0, 0.75, 0.5, 0.25, and 0.125 g. of the complex in a fixed volume of the suspension (100 ml). Carbon dioxide was then passed through these solutions for 12 hours. The solutions were centrifuged, the supernatant liquids titrated for ferrocyanide and ferricyanide, depending on the complex used, and the percentage hydrolysis was calculated (Table I).

TABLE I

$KTiFe(CN)_6$	% Hydrolysis.	$TiFe(CN)_6$	% Hydrolysis.
1.00g.	35.8	1.00g.	26.3
0.75	35.2	0.75	30.2
0.50	43.3	0.50	31.3
		0.25	55.1
		0.125	86.0

Experiments with titanous ferricyanide showed negligible hydrolysis of the complex.

Conductometric Titrations.—The results of conductometric titration are shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2

- (a) 20 ml of $M/30 TiCl_3$ in the cell; $M/10 K_3Fe(CN)_6$ added.
 (b) " " $M/100$ " " " ; $M/50 K_3Fe(CN)_6$ "
 (c) 40 " " $TiCl_3$ " " " ; $M/5 K_3Fe(CN)_6$ "

Potentiometric Titrations.—The potentiometric titrations were performed with the help of a Tinsley potentiometer, using a lamp scale outfit. The ferroferricyanide couple was created at the platinum indicator electrode by adding a little potassium ferricyanide to potassium ferrocyanide solution. Titrations with potassium ferricyanide could be carried out even without adding potassium ferrocyanide to the potassium ferriyanide solution (Fig. 3).

FIG. 3

- (a) 20 ml of $M/100$ - $TiCl_3$ in the cell; $M/50$ - $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added.
 (b) Do; $M/50$ - $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ added.

Thermometric Titrations.—For the thermometric titrations, a well-insulated Dewar's flask of 100 ml capacity was used. The burette was wrapped with asbestos on all sides except for the streak left to make the graduations visible. The reactants were kept for sometime to attain room temperature before actually starting the titrations. Variations in temperature were noted by a Beckmann thermometer. Both direct and reverse titrations were carried out (Fig. 4).

FIG. 4

- (a) 40 ml of $M/100$ - $TiCl_3$ in the cell; $M/5$ - $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added.
 (b) 30 " " $M/60$ - " " " $M/20$ - $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ "
 (c) 20 " " $M/50$ - $TiCl_4$ " " $M/25$ - $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ "

DISCUSSION

The fact that titanous ferrocyanide can be dispersed in a fairly stable state by excess of potassium ferrocyanide and that the other complexes also show a tendency to pass into the colloidal state merely by washing, leads to the conclusion that the various complexes could be endowed with high adsorptive capacities. Adsorption experiments, however, do not provide precise information regarding this behaviour since in only two cases, viz., $\text{KTi}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_6$ and $\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_6$, adsorption of the respective metal ion is seen. In other cases an anomalous behaviour creeps in and instead of positive adsorption of either of the reactants, negative adsorption takes place. The anomaly may be explained either by assuming the hydrolysis of the complex or due to swelling of the freshly precipitated complex. Since the latter effect is not marked, the only factor, which can be taken to be operative, is their hydrolysis. Our experiments on the hydrolysis of titanous and titanous ferrocyanides, where this tendency is exhibited to a fairly high degree, lends support to the former postulate.

The results of chemical analysis show that titanous ferrocyanide and titanous ferrocyanide may be represented by the formula $\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{CN})_6$ and $\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_6$ respectively. It is, however, difficult to say that titanous ferrocyanide having the composition $\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{CN})_6$ is really formed in view of a fairly large redox potential existing in the system:

The value of K for the above reaction (calculated from the oxidation potentials of titanous-titanous and ferro-ferrocyanide couples) is 2.7×10^9 . Such a large value definitely points towards the oxidation of titanous to titanous and the consequent reduction of the ferrocyanide to the ferrocyanide. The reaction of titanous chloride with potassium ferrocyanide can thus be represented as:

the overall reaction being

The titanous ferrocyanide is formed by the reaction:

Results of conductometric, thermometric, and potentiometric titrations between titanium salts and the corresponding potassium ferro- and ferrocyanide provide enough evidence regarding formation of the complexes of types $\text{KTi}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_6$, $\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{CN})_6$ and $\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_6$, thereby confirming the results on the chemical analysis of titanous ferro- and ferrocyanides and titanous ferrocyanide.

A survey of the titration curves would reveal that besides the combining ratio of 1:1 (for which the above mentioned compounds have been enumerated) other combining ratios are possible. Thus the ratios 2:1 and 2:3 [TiCl_3 : $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$; vide curve 2a 3a, and 4a] are seen to exist in the case of conductometric (both direct and reverse), thermometric, and

potentiometric titrations. With these ratios the following stoichiometric reactions may be visualised to take place:

The formation of the above mentioned complexes appears to be highly probable in view of the fact that the titanous ferrocyanide complexes in their freshly precipitated state are liable to adsorb both titanium and ferrocyanide ions. Useful information on the products of interaction of TiCl_3 and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ is available on the basis of conductometric and thermometric titrations. Here the combining ratios of 2:1 and 2:3 [TiCl_3 : $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$; vide curves 2c and 3c] are found and therefore complexes of the type of $\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot \text{TiCl}_3$ and $2\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot \text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ should be formed. These results not only go to show that both Ti^{IV} and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ are adsorbed by the freshly precipitated complex, but it is also found that the metal ion is more strongly adsorbed than the ferrocyanogen ion (0.68 moles of Ti^{IV} per mole of complex). This behaviour, although confirms the results on the adsorptive capacity of titanous ferrocyanide, are in variance with those of other workers for the metal complexes of alkali ferrocyanides.

In the complex formation between TiCl_3 and $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, combining ratios [Ti^{3+} : $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$] such as 3:2, 3:1, and 2:3 (vide curves b, Figs. 2—4) are found by the different methods employed. First two ratios again provide strong evidence for the adsorption of metal ion by the freshly precipitated complex and also for the existence of the compounds having the composition $\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot \text{TiCl}_3$ and $\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 2\text{TiCl}_3$. The last, ratio, viz. 2:3, points towards the formation of the complex $2\text{Ti}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot \text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ which again appears to be an adsorption complex of titanous ferrocyanide.